

DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: This article describes the origins of gender theory, its application, and the specific foundations for the development of women's social activism in the education system.

Keywords: gender theory, feminism, gender equality, women's activism.

Education is of strategic importance and occupies a fundamental position in the life of the individual and society. An individual can master continuous technological innovation with the help of knowledge gained in the educational process, which is organized only with the consideration of gender equality and identity. Feminism, which became an alternative theory of socio-cultural development, was of decisive importance in the emergence of Gender theory. Feminism – (French “feministe”, Latin “femina”-“woman”) is a current that promotes the liberation of women from discrimination, exploring their status as a derivative of social events in society. In the 70s of the XX century, Z. Freud and R. Dissatisfied with the traditional-social science watered down by Hoff's ideas, feminism theorists began to express their cultural, educational, theoretical-methodological approaches typical of Western countries. The penetration of feminist ideas into various areas of culture and education continued at an incredibly rapid pace.

At the beginning of the 70s, the controversy that shocked everyone, the approaches and views towards gender gradually began to sink into the minds of members of society. In practice, the fight against sexual delimitation is also announced in the UN Convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women. These ideas were in the interests of UNESCO activities, as well as organizations that publish manuals for a large number of social, cultural, educational institutions, teachers and employees of the social sphere, and began to serve to eliminate gender delimitation creeds.

Training courses have also arisen that serve to instill gender differences and similarities in the educational process of developed countries in the minds of young people. In the process of implementing this goal, the first task is to improve existing educational programs using new pedagogical technology and modern methods. In improved curricula, equality of boys and girls is important, in addition, the determination of educational materials in all subjects on the basis of gender equality and differences. Such an educational process requires the creation of new educational tools – methodological materials and didactic developments. In turn, educational and methodological materials should be selected in connection with the control tools. It should be noted that the control of the knowledge, skills and abilities of students in Independence should be carried out not only on the basis of mastering, but also on the basis of understanding, practical application of knowledge and identification of creativity skills inherent in each of the boys and girls. This condition not only has a positive effect on the level of knowledge of students, but also educates the owner of

intelligence with a new quality, that is, it greatly helps them to form a unique personality and grow their consciousness, as well as adapt to the social, informative, technological and economic changes of the world. Universal skills play a huge role in educating students and preparing them for future practical activities. The materials of the UN General Assembly's 2000 special session "Women-2000: Gender equality, development and peace", recent research prepared by the World Bank, suggest that there is an inextricable link between economic development and gender equality. The importance of this problem in the development of society can also be clearly observed in recent years on the example of increasing interest in this area in Germany and other European countries. Gender-based education is the sum of educational and educational, educational means that have a comprehensive impact on the preparation of the student for future life.

Ancient culture and the practice of treating women as mother and woman traditionally began to dominate at all levels. Currently, the level of legal culture of the population is growing. Humanity relies on the treasury of spirituality in its way of making women literally equal builders of civil society based on new, democratic principles. One of the most important achievements in pedagogical science is the opening up of educational opportunities based on gender equality and differences. This phenomenon is also of particular value in terms of the point of humanization of Education.

Gender theory approaches the issue of distinguishing characteristics characteristic of men and women from different points of view. The main differences between the sexes are manifested in the social identity of a man and a woman. These differences were formed in society by means of social institutions, norms and cultural views. Social aspects of gender differences are important in this. Gender stratification is the basis for the development of a socio-pedagogical humanitarian system in society and the educational system. The basis of Gender pedagogy is not a dry description of the specific aspects of the education of boys and girls, but educational, social skills that are formed by means of gender stratification.

Although there is an increase in the number of women among the leaders of the enterprise, there is a principle of limiting their activities to the circle of the family. Since the first years of independence, significant efforts have been made in Uzbekistan to overcome this trend and raise the status of women in all aspects of life.

The reforms carried out in our republic are giving positive results in the economic, social, political, cultural and educational achievement of our society among the developed countries of the world. Such changes are being carried out consistently in the educational system, as in all aspects. When our country gained independence, the main task was made to restore our values, realize our identity, form a national idea and ideology in the worldview of students, rebuild the educational system, train personnel who meet all-round mature, modern requirements. The guidelines regarding gender-related hattiharakat are evident in the division of Labor into male and female labor. With the help of these foundations, the development of scientific foundations and technology for the development of social activity of students and girls in the higher education system is a requirement of the period. The educational system is of particular importance in society not only as a factor of technological and socio-economic development, but also as an important strategic tool for spiritual and economic development. Therefore, in our independent country, a lot of attention is paid to the field of education from year to year. The implementation of research on the theory and practice of the development of social activity of students and girls on the basis of a gender

approach in the higher education system of our republic will contribute to the formation of the social activity of future specialists on the basis of the world's newest analytical achievements. The educational significance of social institutions in society such as family, education, religion, culture in the current period in the development of social activity of students and girls increases the effectiveness of this process. In place of the conclusion, we can say that the issue of organizing the educational process on the basis of gender equality and differences of the individual at a time when fundamental changes are taking place in the socio-economic, spiritualintellectual life of Uzbekistan should also become a component of the pedagogical process and research.

In recent years, the institutional framework in this direction has been radically improved, and the Committee on women and gender equality was established under the Senate of the Supreme Assembly. The women's support state target fund was introduced and reorganized as the family and women's support state target fund by Presidential Decree of March 1, 2022. Headed by the president of the Senate Tanzila Norboyeva, initially the Republican women's Community Council began to work, and later, that is, by the Presidential Decree of March 1, the Republican commission on increasing the role of women in society, gender equality and family issues was formed. In March of this year, the state committee for family and women was established. The status and powers of the commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan on issues of gender equality were established at the level of the law. In particular, Article 12 of the law "on equal rights and guarantees of opportunities for women and men" of September 2, 2019 provides for the implementation of a unified state policy in the field of equal rights and opportunities for women and men, achieving real equality of women and men in all spheres of public life, supporting women in socio-legal terms, improving the system, it is envisaged that measures to increase the social and socio-political activity of women on an equal footing with men, the development of proposals for the establishment of special institutions for the protection and assistance of people who are in a difficult situation in life in connection with direct or indirect discrimination on gender, will be carried out by the Commission on issues.

In addition, for the first time in the world experience, the position of a women's activist was introduced in each neighborhood with the aim of developing entrepreneurship, providing employment, working with women's issues on poverty reduction, in a separate, integrated and addressable way.

In the development of women's entrepreneurship, the "women's Entrepreneurship Center" in the regions that help them find their place in society also serves as a real support for women who want to engage in entrepreneurial activities.

Today we are also witnessing the effect of the reforms and reforms carried out in this regard, that the issue of supporting women in our country, ensuring their rights and legitimate interests, is singled out among the main and priority areas of state policy.

The news, which is provided for in the plan of complex measures aimed at implementation in 2022-2023, fully confirms our opinion. In particular, the plan of measures, consisting of 6 main directions and 112 points, aimed at increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life, previously not observed in the practice of world countries.

The discovery of New Horizons in science does not really depend on the age, race, language, nationality and gender of a person. Humanity has realized this fact long ago.

Science and gender equality are integral elements in achieving the development goals outlined in the Sustainable Development Agenda until 2030. Consequently, one of the UN Sustainable Development Goals is to ensure gender equality, expand the rights and opportunities of wives, and ensure women's participation in the public administration system.

On the basis of the goals of sustainable development, the world community has made significant progress in the involvement of women in science. Nevertheless, women still face restrictions on the same front.

According to UNESCO, 3% of the world's experts in information and telecommunications and 5% in natural sciences and mathematics are women. In our country, especially in recent years, significant reforms have been carried out in this direction, giving special importance to strengthening the role of women in social and political life. As a result, women today occupy increasingly leading positions in all spheres of life of our society, making a significant contribution to the development of Education, Culture and science. When we talk about this, first of all, the head of our state recently confirmed

It should be noted that the 69th goal of the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan is precisely the so-called "application of women, ensuring their active participation in the life of society." Within the framework of this goal, including:

- creating an atmosphere of intolerance towards harassment and violence against women in society, ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of women;
- to continue the policy of ensuring gender equality, to increase the sociopolitical activity of women, to implement reforms in their support;
- a number of important tasks are set, such as the acquisition of educational and professional skills of women, comprehensive assistance in finding a suitable job, support of their entrepreneurship, identification of talented young wives and the correct orientation of their abilities.

After all, it is not for nothing that the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his address to the Supreme Assembly, stressed that we should consistently continue and bring to a new modern level the field of development of Science and education, the work that we began to educate our youth as people with deep knowledge, high culture and spirituality.

In recent years, the development of the system of training scientific personnel in our country has become an important factor in this regard. In particular, the Ministry of innovation development and the foundation for Innovative Development and support of innovative ideas were established.

The law " on Science and scientific activities"was also passed. It defined scientific creativity and freedom of information, efficiency and creative competition – as one of the main principles of the field of Science and scientific activity.

A total of 111 scientific projects with a total value of 1.7 trillion soums have been submitted by women so far to the "Olima women grants" practical and innovative projects competition announced by the Ministry of innovation development in 2020. According to the results of the preliminary technical examination, 40 projects were given positive conclusions and 9 projects with a total volume of 10 billion 450 million were financed.

More than 700 female doctors of Sciences and 6 academic women are active in the scientific and educational institutions of the Republic. About three thousand women are

effectively conducting research activities in scientific institutes under the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

Uzbek scientists demonstrate their knowledge and abilities in Chemistry, Biotechnology, Agriculture and many other fields. Their intellectual work is highly appreciated by foreign scientific centers.

The decree of our president of October 29, 2020 approved the concept of the development of science until 2030. It should be noted that this decree is important for the rapid development of economic and social spheres, the widespread use of scientific and innovative potential with the full mobilization of scientific, intellectual and financial resources, the identification of priorities for the continuous reform of Science in the future, the training of self-centered highly qualified personnel.

The decision of the head of our state "on measures to further improve the system of supporting women, ensuring their active participation in the life of society" of March 5, 2021 serves to increase the activity of women in all aspects of the economic, political and social life of our country, to provide comprehensive support for their education and professional skills and employment.

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